

Particle-Level Event Classification for LHC Trigger, with End-to-End Sorting RNNs.

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

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The project consists of designing a long-term memory capable recurrent neural network classifier to predict the underlying physics of LHC proton-proton collisions. The classifier takes the particle flow candidates of a given collision event, and outputs a set of prediction probabilities for 3 classes of physics processes. Furthermore, the project consists of an exploration of backpropagative sorting mechanisms to improve classification efficiency.

ABSTRACT

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The LHC experiment produces an overwhelming amount of data, the vast majority of which consists of Quantum Chromodynamic multi-jet events (QCD). However, physicists are generally concerned with rarer physics processes buried in the QCD background. Culling out this background while maintaining signals of interest is one of the greatest challenges at the LHC. Algorithms for distilling pure signals of interest are called triggers, and generally employ simple rule based filters based on physics based features. However, these features are abstractions of hundreds of stable byproducts of a proton-proton collisions, and therefore constitute a significant reduction in information, much of which could have potentially been used to infer the presence of a signal process. We demonstrate that utilizing long-term memory capable recurrent neural networks (RNNs) we can utilize the full range of information available in a given collision event for the purpose of event classification. Furthermore, we demonstrate the effectiveness of our classifier in both trigger and offline settings. Finally we discuss the potential for further improvements, chiefly related to the ordering of the RNN input, and further extensions of the network backpropagation for this purpose.

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1. Introduction

The CERN Large Hadron Collider (LHC) collides protons every 25 ns. Each collision can undergo any of thousands of physics processes. However QCD multi-jet events, constitute the vast majority of collision events. Rarer events such as W boson (W+jets) and top-pair production ($t\bar{t}$), are selected in real time by a set of rule-based algorithms known as the trigger system which exploit the presence of rare features in the event. Ultimately the trigger system decides what events to store for further analysis and what events to throw away. There are several qualities of a well-constructed trigger:

1. Eliminate the QCD background contamination.
2. Achieve good signal efficiency across diverse signal constituents within each desired channel.
3. Further cull out more numerous signal events if their rate is excessive.

Ultimately the goal of the trigger is to mitigate the magnitude of computing resources dedicated to storing, distributing and analyzing data from the LHC. The quality of a trigger dictates how much of the available computing power at the LHC can be redistributed to analyses aimed toward discovering new physics instead of needlessly processing QCD background events that have been erroneously tagged as interesting physics processes.

Traditional trigger systems are rule based, and operate on physics inspired high-level event features which constitute a drastic reduction in the total information available in an event. Our proposed trigger system in contrast would utilize the full range of information available among the reconstructed particles of an event. We utilize the variable length sequences of particle flow (PF) candidates for each event. This is the list of stable byproducts of the event reconstructed from the raw detector data. To infer the underlying physics of a collision event from this PF candidate collection, which generally consists of hundreds of particles, we employ long-term memory capable Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs).

Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)[1] and Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU)[2] RNNs, employ various gating mechanisms to both remember and forget information as they scan through a data sequence. Consequently, these networks have the ability to infer from information found in distant parts of a data sequence while maintaining model simplicity, and the ability to handle variable input sizes. To construct our classifier, we train LSTM and GRU RNNs on labelled simulation data. The trained classifier can then later be used in a trigger setting on the PF candidates of real detector data to infer the underlying physics of proton-proton collisions.

2. Related Work

Machine learning has been used before in high energy physics to solve various classification and regression problems. These include but are not limited to calorimeter energy reconstruction [3][4], and electron/jet classification[5]. Similar work on event classification has been done with recurrent neural networks that take as input the 4-momenta of the reconstructed particles paired with jet clustering inspired features generated by recursive neural nets [6]. However, the network inputs and overall objective of our work is decidedly different. Chiefly, we impose no structure related to jet physics on our features so that the classifier is unconstrained by the arbitrary groupings of jet clustering algorithms. Furthermore, we utilize the full range of particle features instead of relying solely on the 4-momenta. In addition our dataset is explicitly configured to mimic a trigger setting, and we incorporate $t\bar{t}$ in addition to QCD and W+Jets for a 3-way classification problem.

3. Data Composition

We generated data for W+jets, $t\bar{t}$, and QCD events from the PYTHIA8 event generation package. We then feed the generated particles into the DELPHES package with the default CMS card to simulate the detector response. Through a process of filtering the generated data we end with only those events which would pass a typical yet loose high level trigger cut of 1 lepton with >25 GeV and an isolation cut on the

lepton of <20% relative to the particle flow candidates. The events are then shuffled with equal parts of each event class to maximize the exposure of the network to a diverse set of inputs unhindered by the relative rarity of the signal classes W +jets, and $t\bar{t}$. Each set of PF candidates is represented as a numpy array of 801 rows of 19 features. 801 is a rough upper bound on the possible number of PF candidates plus the lepton. The 19 features include:

- The Cartesian 4-momentum (4).
- The transverse momentum (1).
- Phi and eta of the 4-momentum (2).
- Vertex location (3).
- Cross isolation values for each PF candidate relative to other types of PF candidates (3).
- A one-hot representation of the PF candidate/lepton type (5).
- The particle charge. (1).

Since the number of particles is almost always significantly less than 801 we pad the end with zeros. The zero padding is masked out during training.

4. Training and Model Architecture

For our model we utilize the Keras (<https://github.com/fchollet/keras>) machine learning library with Theano[7] backend. We use LSTM and GRU RNNs to aggregate the input sequence into a fixed size encoding, which we then feed into a 3 node softmax layer. Each of the 3 nodes corresponds to the predicted probability that the input event corresponds to a particular physics process. The LSTM and GRU models utilize the keras defaults of a tanh activation, with hard_sigmoid inner activation. For each network training we utilize early stopping with a patience of 8 epochs and a hard cap of 100 epochs. Training a single model takes roughly 12-24 hours over the course of 30-80 epochs on a single GeForce GTX 1080 GPU.

The best internal width of the recurrent layers was determined by 3 redundant runs for each width trained on a different K-fold subsets of the training set each totaling 300,000 events. We found that for LSTMs a fixed width of 50 gave varied results, but the best overall, and so in the interest of achieving the best validation performance we proceeded with this width. Using several redundant runs we tested the effects of the network architecture (GRU or LSTM) on the classification performance. In general, the GRU architecture out-performed the LSTM architecture, and we found that standardizing the particle features (i.e. subtracting each feature by the mean over all training samples and dividing by the standard deviation) improved the results further. The zero padding was ignored during standardization to preserve the masking behaviour of the network.

Model	Validation Accuracy	ROC Area Under Curve
GRU-standardized	95.26% ± .11%	0.9958 ± 1.6e-5
GRU	94.74% ± .26%	0.9953 ± 2.5e-4
LSTM	93.97% ± .35%	0.9939 ± 6.6e-4

Figures (1,2). (Left) Validation accuracy versus number of nodes in each recurrent node. (above) Validation accuracy and AUC for LSTM, GRU, and GRU with the data standardized. Error bounds are measured in standard deviations of the distribution of several trainings

5. Results

We present the results of our best classifier trained with a GRU and standardized data evaluated with $t\bar{t}$ the rarest event type, as the positive class and W +Jets and QCD as the collective negative class.

Figures (3,4,5) : (Left) The plane $x+y+z=1$ corresponding to the set of possible probabilities among 3 classes.(Middle) A set of softmax predictions evaluated on the plane in 2D as if the vector $(1,1,1)$ were in the center of the graph and pointing at the viewer. (Right) The graph viewed under a logarithmic transformation, so that the points are pulled out the corners and edges.

For visualization we use a 3D extension of a typical plot of the prediction separations. The 3D separation plot is a projective geometry of the prediction probabilities in 3D space confined to the plane $x+y+z=1$ and bound by the conditions $x+y, x+z, y+z \leq 1$ Figures (3,4). The coordinates of each point corresponds to a softmax prediction of the classifier, and each color corresponds to the true class to which the event belongs. Each line corresponds to a threshold point of the classifier at a fixed efficiency of the positive class. Each threshold allows one to visualize the distribution of predictions on either side of a single point in a one versus rest ROC curve. For example, consider the class in the top vertex as the positive class, evaluated against the other two. In this case, moving the threshold up would result in a classifier with lower efficiency for the positive class, and lower contamination from the other two classes. Consequently each threshold line has an associated true positive rate (efficiency) and false positive rate (contamination). Since an effective classifier will generally have very few predictions in the region in the center of the triangle (this would correspond to high uncertainty about the nature of an event), it is better to evaluate the plot under a logarithmic transformation to pull the data out of the edges of the triangle; Figure (5).

Figure 6: The best GRU classifier visualized on a logarithmic projective geometry, with each threshold line corresponding to a row in the table. Each row gives a fixed $t\bar{t}$ efficiency with the corresponding contamination rates for W+Jets and QCD.

Figure 6 outlines the contamination rates of our best GRU classifier at several fixed efficiencies. At 95% efficiency our classifier has 1.19%, and 1.40% contamination rates for W+Jets and QCD respectively corresponding to a two order of magnitude reduction in the background with only a modest loss in the $t\bar{t}$ signal. For now we consider W+Jets to be a background process, since it greatly outnumbers. Farther up the table we see that at 79.3% efficiency we can reduce the background contamination by another order of magnitude, and a total of 4 orders of magnitude at 60% efficiency. At 40% efficiency the background is completely removed. Our ability to completely remove the background is nothing short of extraordinary. In an offline setting utilizing this classifier at low efficiencies would be an incredible analysis tool. However, in a trigger setting we would like a classifier that does not throw out certain parts of the signal over others. For example, we would like to maintain signals corresponding to a broad range of

energies, even if we incur some contamination. Unfortunately, separating from the background becomes more difficult at lower energies.

Figures (7,8). (left) A log-scale plot of the frequency of events with different energies for the most energetic lepton. (right) Each bin normalized to 1.0, giving the relative proportions of the events of different classes.

Figures 7 and 8 show the proportions of each type of physics process that remain after a loose high level trigger cut. At higher lepton energies $t\bar{t}$ is far more numerous. Figure 9 shows the contamination rates for W+jets and QCD. Note that the contamination rate is higher for larger PT indicating that the classifier predict $t\bar{t}$ more often at these energies, however the large standard errors indicate that the contamination arises from a small number of events. Figures 10 and 11 show the individual class efficiencies as a function of the lepton PT at fixed efficiencies of 95% and 99%. For the purposes of this paper we will focus on the green dots corresponding to $t\bar{t}$ as the positive class. At 95% the classifier clearly loses far more events at lower energies. However, at 99% this effect is largely mitigated.

Figures (9,10,11). (left) The contamination rates as a function of the PT of the most energetic lepton for W+Jets (blue) and QCD (red) taking $t\bar{t}$ as the positive class at 95% fixed efficiency. (middle,right) The efficiency versus the lepton PT at 95% and 99% overall fixed efficiencies respectively. $t\bar{t}$ bar (green), W+Jets (blue), QCD (red).

Finally we analyse how our classifier reduces the over-all frequency of events for the QCD multi-jet, and W+jets background at 95% and 99% fixed efficiency. At 99% fixed efficiency we can reduce the total number of events from 487Hz to 44.45 Hz. At 95% we reduce the frequency to a minuscule 8.17 Hz. This constitutes a significant reduction in the QCD background and W+jets; a significant decrease in the amount of resources that must be dedicated to the unnecessary processing of events.

Figures (12, 13, 14, 15): (pi-charts) Green=QCD, Blue=W+Jets, Purple=ttbar. The proportions of the event frequencies after a loose high level trigger, and the GRU classifier at 99% and 95% fixed efficiency respectively. (table) the frequencies of each class of collision event after the high level trigger cut and the GRU classifier cuts.

6. An Exploration of End-To-End Sorting

We find that the performance of our classifier depends in part on the order in which the particles are fed into the recurrent layer. Figure 16 summarizes the performance of a GRU classifier trained on data sorted by different physics based metrics.

Sorting	Validation Accuracy	ROC Area Under Curve
MaxLepDeltaR_des	94.74% ± .26%	0.9953 ± 2.5e-4
MaxLepDeltaR_asc	94.48%	0.9943
MaxLepDeltaPhi	94.08%	0.9938
Random	93.65%	0.9933

Figure 16: The validation accuracies and ROC Areas Under Curve for GRU classifiers trained on data sorted via several different metrics. See Appendix 1 for further explanations of the sorting metrics..

One of the goals of this project was to design a network that learns the best way to order the PF candidates when feeding them into the GRU layer. However the principle challenge of learning a sorting order is that sorting is not a differentiable function and therefore the sorting metric cannot be learned by normal back-propagation. To address this issue I employed several methods, all of which were tested with the toy problem of trying to learn to sort a list of random vectors by their L2 norm. The loss to be minimized for each problem was the mean square error between the output list and the correctly sorted list. This formulation of the loss is suboptimal for solving the toy problem directly, however somewhat realistic with respect to the actual problem at hand. The challenge after-all is to learn a sorting that optimally enables a GRU to minimize the categorical cross entropy in a classification problem. Therefore the actual loss being minimized has little connection to the sorting problem directly.

My first approach to learning the sorting metric was to fake the gradient by approximating it with the finite difference in loss between two separate forward passes of the network. In one pass the sorting metric was randomly perturbed, resulting in a random local search from which the gradient could be approximated. This method did not work well, likely because the random perturbations, unlike backpropagation, had no sense of a good direction in which to explore the parameter space.

My next approach was to attempt to make the sorting differentiable by generating a sorting matrix from the metric values using a neural network. I define the sorting matrix as a matrix which sorts the unsorted sequence when multiplied from the left. The application of this transformation would essentially tie the gradients of the sorted sequence to a learned metric sequence evaluated from the input sequence via a set of stacked DNNs whose weights are learned. My first implementation incorporated a type of attentive recurrent network called a pointer network[8], which had succeeded in solving small instances of difficult combinatorial optimization problems such as the traveling salesman problem. However, the pointer net generated sorting matrix tended to not be sparse or injective, meaning that data would be mixed together and dropped respectively. These issues were exaggerated as the problem grew in size. Furthermore, the GPU and memory resources required by the pointer net grew cubically with the size of the problem. I decided that it would be infeasible to sort an 801 element list with this method, so I moved to trying to solve only the smaller problem of sorting 8-10 elements at a time using DNNs, then applying this

solution repeatedly. This method also initially failed from sparsity and injectivity issues. However, by using some clever regularizers that rewarded sparsity and injectivity over correctness, and using the sorting matrix as the target instead of the output sequence, I achieved satisfactory result at least on this subproblem. Unfortunately, this method had further issues related to the model complexity slowing down or causing catastrophic failures in the compilation step both for theano and tensorflow.

Figures (17,18,19,20): (far-left) A sorting matrix that is not injective. (middle-left) A sorting matrix that is not sparse. (middle-right) A perfectly sparse and injective sorting matrix. (far-right) The sorting matrix generated from a point net.

However the relative success of this method for short lists, and the fact that the network employed at least an $O(n^2)$ approach for an $O(n \log(n))$ problem lead me to believe that I could construct a differentiable function to generate a sorting matrix from an input list that operated in $O(n^2)$ space and time by essentially contriving the exact network weights that a DNN would need to learn to solve the problem. Indeed I derived a transformation within the search space of a multilayer DNN that could perfectly (assuming the differences in value were greater than a small epsilon) generate a sorting matrix from a list of unsorted floating point numbers:

$$\delta^+(x) = \frac{1}{\epsilon} * \text{relu}(-x + \epsilon); x \in [0, \infty) \quad U(x) = \delta^+(([1 \dots n - 1] - \sum_j \delta^+(\text{relu}(x_j)))^2)$$

However as it turns out, the gradient of this transformation is zero everywhere. So I began looking into how to alter the gradients directly with Theano, but realized that if I was going to alter the gradients, I might as well alter them to be exactly what they should be, and solve the sorting problem in $O(n \log(n))$ time with quicksort, doing away with the $O(n^2)$ sorting matrix entirely.

I contended that the gradient for a given metric value should be the sum of the feature gradients of the particle in the sorted list from which that metric was derived. This gradient would then be passed back through the stack of DNNs that created it in order to optimally alter the weights to create the optimal sorting. For the toy problem of sorting vectors by their norm this worked partially, but only when the metric gradients were essentially denoised by setting to zero the gradients with the lowest absolute value. In particular dropping the gradient of any metric value less than 90% of the magnitude of the largest such gradient resulted in a noticeable improvement. With this alteration the loss would attenuate at least up to a point. The gradient of each metric value ostensibly indicates the direction and magnitude that it should be altered in order get closer to the optimal sorting. However, altering every metric value at once would be like moving every element in the sequence at once. In contrast, setting to zero the smallest gradients limits the network to only making switches in the sequence that result in a steep reduction in the loss.

Unfortunately this method did not succeed in improving the classification loss for the problem at hand even when it was explicitly fed the features of the highest energy lepton, (a set of features necessary for the network to at least re-implement the sorting metrics tried previously). Ultimately the network performance was comparable only the networks trained on randomly sorted data.

Regardless, one can at least conclude that within the context of this problem sorting directly with neural networks is a poor choice compared to sorting with traditional algorithms and fixing the gradients so that they pass to the correct metric value. It may be that an improvement in the sorting is possible if the GRU and DNN stack for building the sorting metric began in a state targeted toward an existing sorting metric. It is possible that the sorting could be improved from that starting configuration. However, if that

experiment should fail, it would certainly cast serious doubt on the assertion that the sorting could be improved purely by backpropagating the classification loss.

7. Appendix: Previous Work on Sorting

In a previous iteration of the project we tested a wider range of physics based sorting metrics. We tested several metrics calculated with respect to the most energetic lepton in each event. We tested ascending and descending orderings of these metrics defined in Figure 21.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{PT_ET} &: p_i^\perp \\
 \text{MaxLepDeltaPhi} &: \delta_i^{\phi_{max}} = \phi_{max} - \phi_i \in [-\pi, \pi] \\
 \text{MaxLepDeltaEta} &: \delta_i^{\eta_{max}} = \eta_{max} - \eta_i \in [-\pi, \pi] \\
 \text{MaxLepDeltaR} &: R_i = \sqrt{(\delta_i^{\phi_{max}})^2 + (\delta_i^{\eta_{max}})^2} \\
 \text{MaxLepKt} &: K_i^\perp = \min((p_{max}^\perp)^2, (p_i^\perp)^2) R_i \\
 \text{MaxLepAntiKt} &: K_i^{-1} = \min((p_{max}^\perp)^{-2}, (p_i^\perp)^{-2}) R_i
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 21: The definition of several sorting metrics. *PT_ET* is simply the transverse momentum of the particle. *MaxLepDeltaPhi* and *MaxLepDeltaEta* are the azimuthal angle and pseudo-rapidities of each particle relative to the most energetic lepton. *MaxLepDeltaR* is the Cartesian distance of these two values. *MaxLepKt* and *MaxLepAntiKt* incorporate the transverse momentum of the particle and the lepton.

We found that the descending varieties of the metrics that included R_i generally performed best. Descending orderings of R_i put the most energetic lepton at the end of the list, which essentially minimizes the probability that it is forgotten by an LSTM. Figure 22 outlines the validation AUC scores for single trainings of each ordering. Our conclusion from this set of trainings is the same as our conclusion from more recent results: that ordering indeed matters, and can improve a long term memory capable recurrent neural network's powers of inference.

Figure 22: (left) ROC curves for LSTM networks trained on several sorting metrics and their corresponding AUCs. (right) The ROC curves shown with logarithmic False Positive Rates (FPR).

8. References

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